

EMPOWERING WOMEN IN LEADERSHIP: OPPORTUNITIES AND BARRIERS IN NIGERIAN CORPORATE GOVERNANCE

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Abstract

This paper investigates the challenges and opportunities in advancing women into leadership positions within Nigerian corporate governance. As gender diversity is increasingly recognised as a critical component of effective leadership globally, understanding the unique barriers women face in Nigeria is essential for developing meaningful interventions. This research centres on the obstacles that hinder women's progression into leadership roles in Nigeria's corporate sector, focusing on cultural norms, organisational policies, and access to professional networks. Employing a qualitative research methodology, the study draws on in-depth interviews conducted with female executives across various industries in Nigeria. These interviews offer valuable insights into how deep-seated cultural expectations and organisational biases shape women's experiences striving for leadership roles. The research also examines the significant impact of limited access to mentorship programs and professional networks, often critical for career advancement. Additionally, the study explores potential pathways for progress, highlighting targeted corporate initiatives and supportive government policies to increase women's representation in leadership positions. The findings reveal that while there has been some progress in improving the representation of women in Nigerian corporate leadership, substantial barriers remain. These barriers, deeply rooted in cultural and structural factors, continue to impede the advancement of women. However, the study identifies promising opportunities for improvement by implementing strategic initiatives such as comprehensive mentorship programs and cultivating inclusive organisational cultures that actively promote gender diversity. The research emphasises the necessity of a focused and strategic approach to dismantling these barriers. It offers actionable recommendations for corporate leaders and policymakers committed to empowering women in leadership roles. This paper contributes to the ongoing discourse on gender equality in leadership by providing a nuanced analysis of the Nigerian context. It offers practical recommendations to enhance women's participation in corporate governance, emphasising strategies that can be effectively implemented within the Nigerian business environment. The insights from this study are intended to guide corporate leaders and policymakers in fostering greater diversity and inclusion, ultimately leading to more equitable and effective governance structures in Nigeria.

Keywords: Cultural barriers, Gender diversity, Governance, Inclusion, Mentorship, Women in leadership

1. INTRODUCTION

Corporate governance in Nigeria has undergone significant evolution since the country's independence, shaped by national policies and international frameworks prioritising transparency, accountability, and inclusivity. Despite these advancements, gender diversity within corporate leadership remains a pressing issue. The underrepresentation of women in governance structures can be attributed to a complex interplay of cultural norms, socio-economic barriers, and institutional constraints that limit women's participation in leadership roles (Adejuge, 2024).

Gender dynamics in Nigerian corporate governance are further complicated by regional, ethnic, and religious differences, which shape societal perceptions of gender roles and create varied experiences for women across different sectors. This complexity makes it imperative to understand women's specific challenges in attaining leadership positions and develop targeted strategies to address these challenges within Nigerian corporate governance. Recent discourses have increasingly emphasised the importance of diversity and inclusion in corporate governance. Diversity, defined as a blend of skills, abilities, genders, ages, cultures, and ethnic backgrounds within a company's workforce, significantly impacts a company's performance and bottom line (Tamunomiebi & John-Eke, 2020; Oxford Dictionary, n.d.). A diverse workforce attracts and retains clients, enhances value creation and innovation, and increases employment and productivity, aligning with the United Nations Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 8, which promotes sustained, inclusive, and sustainable economic growth, full and productive employment, and decent work for all (United Nations, 2021).

Gender diversity, an essential facet of diversity, aligns with SDG 5, which aims to achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls (United Nations, n.d.). Ensuring equal opportunities for women in the workplace, including leadership roles, is critical for achieving gender-based equality. In corporate governance, gender diversity on boards is increasingly recognised as a hallmark of sound governance. It refers to the presence and proportion of female directors on corporate boards, which contemporary organisations view as a critical value driver in organisational strategy and governance (Carter et al., 2003; Duncan & Nzulwa, 2016). Research indicates that board gender diversity positively influences the quality of financial reporting, likely due to the unique socio-psychological traits of female executives, such as greater risk aversion and lower propensity for deceptive practices (Damagum et al., 2014).

Promoting gender diversity on corporate boards has been advocated for its business benefits and as a matter of gender equity. Diverse boards are more effective in monitoring management (Kamalath & Masselot, 2019) and are essential for corporate sustainability, particularly regarding Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) compliance. Diverse perspectives on a board help prevent groupthink and enhance decision-making processes. Studies have shown that women bring different leadership philosophies, attend more board meetings, and significantly contribute to the group's collective intelligence (Pieters, 2012). Moreover, increasing the representation of women on boards expands the talent pool for executive and supervisory roles, positively affecting organisational performance. Companies with a higher percentage of female directors also demonstrate better corporate social responsibility, suggesting that adding more women to boards could enhance philanthropic efforts (Fodio & Oba, 2011).

Empirical evidence supports that companies with a significant number of female directors tend to outperform those with fewer or no female directors regarding financial performance and governance quality. Such companies often adopt a more holistic view of stakeholder interests than their male-dominated counterparts, reinforcing that board diversity is critical to superior performance (Mohammed & Ahmad, 2017a). Legislative measures are a powerful tool to ensure gender diversity on corporate boards, especially in contexts where women are underrepresented in senior corporate roles. Legal frameworks have been shown to significantly influence board composition (Grosvold & Brammer, 2011). Importantly, including women on boards has a positive and significant impact on a company's success, suggesting that gender diversity correlates with better financial outcomes. However, promoting women to board positions should not solely be viewed from a financial performance perspective but also as an issue of social equity. This is particularly relevant in developing economies like Nigeria, where the representation of women in top management roles remains relatively low (Oba & Fodio, 2013; Mohammed & Ahmad, 2017b).

Despite these challenges, recent data indicate a positive trend in the representation of women on Nigerian corporate boards across various sectors, including manufacturing, conglomerates, general services, financial services, and banking. From 2016 to 2020, there was a notable increase in female representation on boards (DCSL Corporate Services Limited, 2023a). By 2023, many corporate organisations in Nigeria had appointed

women to leadership positions, leading to significant improvements in profit margins, innovation, and productivity (DCSL Corporate Services Limited, 2023b; Bailey, 2023a). This progress can be attributed to several factors:

- a. The introduction of Nigerian regulations providing guidelines for gender inclusion on boards.
- b. The rise of networking, role modelling, and mentorship programs for women aspiring to board positions, facilitated by organisations such as Women in Management, Business, and Public Service (WIMBIZ) and the Institute of Directors (IOD) mentoring programs (Access Corporation, 2022; WIMBOARDS, 2023; Institute of Directors Nigeria, 2023).
- c. The emergence of female leaders in top corporate roles inspires other women to pursue similar positions.

2. STRUCTURE AND KEY PLAYERS IN NIGERIAN CORPORATE GOVERNANCE

The corporate governance landscape in Nigeria has evolved significantly over the years and has been influenced by historical, socio-economic, and regulatory factors. Initially perceived as a colonial imposition, the Nigerian corporate governance framework had to adapt to the country's unique socio-economic landscape, which involved tailoring Western governance models to fit local realities. The corporate governance structure in Nigeria primarily revolves around a combination of laws, regulations, and codes of best practices that foster transparency, accountability, and fairness in business operations.

Key players in Nigerian corporate governance include government regulatory bodies such as the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC), the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE), and the Corporate Affairs Commission (CAC). These bodies enforce compliance with governance codes and regulations, including the Nigerian Code of Corporate Governance 2018, which provides comprehensive guidelines on board composition, executive compensation, risk management, and stakeholder engagement.

The corporate governance framework also involves a network of private and public companies, financial institutions, shareholders, and board members, all of whom are critical in decision-making processes. The effectiveness of corporate governance in Nigeria has been the subject of much debate, with studies highlighting the importance of specific attributes of boards, such as size, diversity, and independence, in impacting the financial performance, stakeholder involvement, and risk management practices of Nigerian companies (Maier & Yurtoğlu, 2022; Mahfoudh, 2024; Esan et al., 2022).

3. GENDER COMPOSITION OF CORPORATE BOARDS IN NIGERIA

Gender diversity in corporate governance has emerged as a significant component of efficient governance processes and organisational resilience. The gender composition of corporate boards in Nigeria reflects broader societal and cultural dynamics that have historically limited women's participation in leadership roles. The traditional gender roles entrenched in Nigerian society have significantly hindered women's advancement in corporate leadership. Cultural norms that relegated women to domestic roles have historically excluded them from governance and decision-making processes, and when women were permitted to participate, their roles were often symbolic (Allanana Makama, 2013).

The push towards greater gender diversity on corporate boards has been shaped by various policy interventions, including the introduction of quotas and affirmative action programs aimed at increasing female representation. These measures, while sometimes successful, have also sparked debates about the qualifications and legitimacy of female leaders appointed under such frameworks (Ukachukwu, 2024). Studies have demonstrated that gender-diverse boards are more likely to exhibit improved financial performance, stronger stakeholder engagement, and enhanced risk management practices (Mahfoudh, 2024; Esan et al., 2022).

Despite these policy efforts, the progress towards achieving gender parity on Nigerian corporate boards has been slow and uneven. The effectiveness of these measures is still under scrutiny, and their impact on organizational outcomes remains a critical area for further research. Moreover, the intersection of gender with other social factors, such as ethnicity and socio-economic status, complicates efforts to achieve gender parity. Women from marginalized groups often face compounded discrimination, further limiting their opportunities for advancement (Agbaje, 2024).

National legislation and corporate governance frameworks have begun to address these disparities, though cultural change remains slow. The persistent underrepresentation of women in corporate governance reflects

not only the challenges in the regulatory environment but also the deep-seated cultural biases and systemic barriers that continue to exist within Nigerian society. Addressing these challenges requires a multifaceted approach, involving policy reform, corporate commitment to diversity and inclusion, and broader societal change to dismantle stereotypes and support women's advancement into leadership positions.

4. OPPORTUNITIES FOR WOMEN IN CORPORATE LEADERSHIP

The post-independence development of corporate governance in Nigeria has been deeply influenced by regulatory reforms, economic transitions, and evolving societal expectations. These factors have significantly shaped the representation of genders in leadership roles within Nigerian companies, reflecting broader trends in governance practices. Recent years have witnessed an increasing emphasis on gender diversity, board independence, and sustainable governance systems as crucial components influencing corporate performance. Scholars like Ezeani et al. (2021), Hsu and Yang (2022), and Erin et al. (2021) underscore the importance of these elements in driving organisational success and maintaining accountability.

Several legal frameworks and policies have been implemented to support gender diversity, including the Companies and Allied Matters Act (CAMA) 2020 and the Nigerian Code of Corporate Governance. These frameworks aim to foster gender-balanced leadership and enhance corporate governance by ensuring diverse representation on boards. The growing awareness and advocacy for gender diversity in corporate governance reflect a broader shift towards more inclusive governance practices, driven by both regulatory mandates and societal expectations.

Corporate best practices and initiatives are increasingly promoting female leadership, recognizing the value that gender diversity brings to decision-making and corporate strategy. Research by Vafaei et al. (2020) and Sunita (2022) demonstrates that gender-inclusive boards contribute to better decision-making processes, enhanced financial outcomes, and more effective crisis management. These findings are particularly pertinent given the lessons learned from the COVID-19 pandemic, which underscored the need for robust governance frameworks capable of managing crises and ensuring the integrity of financial reporting (Hsu & Yang, 2022; Ayeni-Agbaje, 2024).

The impact of gender diversity on financial performance and stakeholder engagement is further supported by case studies of successful women in Nigerian corporate governance. These case studies highlight the transformative role that women leaders play in driving corporate sustainability and fostering a culture of ethical business practices. For instance, integrating corporate social responsibility (CSR) into governance frameworks has become essential for companies seeking to maintain a competitive edge in both local and global markets. Scholars like Erin et al. (2021) and Gull et al. (2022) link governance practices to the quality of sustainability reporting and CSR initiatives, emphasising the need for transparent and accountable leadership.

5. REGULATORY AND POLICY FRAMEWORKS FOR GENDER INCLUSIVITY

Regulatory bodies such as the Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) and the Nigerian Stock Exchange (NSE) have been pivotal in shaping corporate governance practices by establishing codes and guidelines to improve transparency and accountability. For example, the 2018 Revised Nigerian Code of Corporate Governance represents a significant step toward fostering better governance standards with an emphasis on promoting gender diversity and board effectiveness (Ozili, 2023). This regulatory framework seeks to align Nigerian corporate governance practices with international best practices, thereby enhancing the credibility and performance of Nigerian firms in the global arena.

Gender quotas, ethical considerations, and political mandates have become central strategies in advocating for equitable representation, ensuring that women have greater opportunities to ascend to senior leadership roles (Garcia-Sanchez, 2023). These policies reflect a growing recognition of the necessity to dismantle systemic barriers and create inclusive governance practices that foster fair representation.

6. THE IMPACT OF GENDER-INCLUSIVE LEADERSHIP ON CORPORATE PERFORMANCE

Research consistently shows that gender diversity on corporate boards positively impacts financial performance, decision-making, and stakeholder engagement. Studies by Vafaei et al. (2020) and Sunita (2022) demonstrate that gender-inclusive boards are more effective and lead to improved company outcomes. This growing body of evidence supports the need for regulatory frameworks that prioritise gender

diversity as a core component of corporate governance.

Moreover, Nigeria's corporate social responsibility (CSR) initiatives have significantly empowered women economically and socially. For example, Nigerian banks use CSR to support women's healthcare, financial independence, and career development. These initiatives contribute to gender inclusivity by addressing the multifaceted needs of women and ensuring their active participation in the economy.

7. BARRIERS TO WOMEN'S LEADERSHIP IN CORPORATE GOVERNANCE

Despite the recognized benefits of gender diversity, achieving gender inclusivity within Nigerian corporate governance is hindered by a multitude of challenges. These barriers are deeply embedded in the structural, cultural, and institutional fabric of the corporate landscape

7.1. Cultural and Societal Norms Affecting Women's Participation

Cultural and societal expectations often play a significant role in limiting women's participation in leadership roles within corporate governance. Respondents highlighted how deep-rooted gender roles can be an impediment:

Respondent A stated, "In our culture, women are often expected to prioritize family over career. This societal pressure creates an internal conflict for many women aspiring to leadership positions."

Respondent B noted, "There's an unspoken rule in many corporate settings that leadership is a man's job. Women who break this norm are often seen as aggressive or too ambitious."

7.2. Workplace Biases and Stereotypes

Biases and stereotypes in the workplace can hinder women's progress to leadership positions. These biases often manifest in subtle but significant ways, affecting women's career trajectories.

Respondent C shared, "Even in meetings, it's common for men to dominate the conversation, and when women speak up, they are either interrupted or their ideas are dismissed. It creates an environment where we constantly have to prove ourselves."

Respondent D added, "There's a preconceived notion that women are not as decisive or strong in leadership roles, which affects promotion decisions and overall workplace dynamics."

7.3. Lack of Mentorship and Networking Opportunities

The absence of mentorship and networking opportunities is another barrier that prevents women from ascending to leadership roles. Mentorship is crucial for career development, yet it is often less accessible to women.

Respondent E remarked, "Mentorship is often informal and male-dominated. Women, especially in male-led industries, are not always invited to networking events where important career discussions happen."

Respondent F observed, "I've seen male colleagues be fast-tracked for promotion because of their close relationships with senior leaders. Women don't always have the same access to these networks."

7.4. Challenges in Balancing Work-Life Dynamics

Balancing work and life dynamics remains a significant challenge for women aiming for leadership roles. Expectations around caregiving and domestic responsibilities disproportionately affect women's career progression.

Respondent G emphasized, "The expectation that women must balance both a career and the majority of family responsibilities is a huge barrier. It's like we're expected to perform double duty."

Respondent H mentioned, "Many women I know have turned down promotions or leadership roles because they couldn't reconcile the demands of the job with their family responsibilities."

7.5. Gender Pay Gap and Limited Access to Leadership Development Programs

The gender pay gap and restricted access to leadership development opportunities further compound the challenges faced by women in corporate governance.

Respondent I stated, "There is a noticeable pay gap between men and women even in the same roles,

which is discouraging. It sends a message that our work and leadership are not valued equally."

Respondent J added, "Leadership development programs are often geared towards men, or they don't consider the unique challenges faced by women. There's a need for more inclusive and accessible programs that encourage women's leadership."

8. STRATEGIES FOR OVERCOMING BARRIERS

1. Policy Recommendations for Inclusive Corporate Governance: To enhance gender inclusivity within corporate governance, several policy changes are needed. These include implementing mandatory gender quotas on corporate boards and leadership positions, providing regular gender sensitivity training, and enforcing equal opportunity policies. Respondent 11 emphasizes that "*setting a minimum percentage of women in certain positions and ensuring compliance through legislation and assessments*" is critical for driving gender inclusivity. Similarly, Respondent 12 notes that "*introducing quotas can be a powerful tool to increase female representation and ensure women have a seat at the table.*"

2. Role of Government, Private Sector, and Civil Society in Driving Change: The government, private sector, and civil society play significant roles in advancing gender inclusivity. Legal and regulatory measures, such as setting quotas and enforcing compliance, are essential for holding organisations accountable. As Respondent 9 states, "*Implementing laws that mandate a certain percentage of women on boards can drive change.*" Civil society's role in advocacy and raising awareness is also crucial. Respondent 10 underscores this, highlighting "*the role of cultural orientation and advocacy in changing societal norms, particularly in regions where cultural beliefs significantly hinder women's participation.*"

3. Developing Mentorship and Sponsorship Programs: Establishing structured mentorship programs for women are pivotal in helping them navigate corporate challenges and advance their careers. Respondent 12 suggests that "*mentorship programs tailored for women can provide the guidance and support needed to advance in their careers,*" which is echoed by Respondent 14's recommendation for "*policies that increase female representation on boards through intentional inclusion efforts.*"

4. Encouraging Diversity and Inclusion Training within Organizations: Regular training on diversity and inclusion is vital for fostering an inclusive corporate culture. Respondent 8 advocates for "*training to raise awareness about unconscious biases and ensuring equal opportunities for all voices in the boardroom.*" This training helps employees recognise and address their biases, creating a more inclusive and supportive environment.

9. POLICIES TO ENHANCE GENDER INCLUSIVITY IN NIGERIA

1. Mandatory Gender Quotas on Corporate Boards: Implementing mandatory gender quotas is a significant step towards ensuring women's representation in leadership roles. Respondent 11 asserts that "*introducing quotas can be a powerful tool to increase female representation and ensure women have a seat at the table.*" This approach promotes equality and brings diverse perspectives to decision-making, enhancing innovation and overall company performance.

2. Gender Sensitivity Training: Regular gender sensitivity training for employees at all levels is crucial in combating biases and fostering inclusive workplace cultures. As Respondent 12 points out, "*regular gender sensitivity training is crucial for changing mindsets and fostering a more inclusive workplace culture.*" These sessions help employees recognise their prejudices and understand the importance of diversity.

3. Enforcing Equal Opportunity Policies: Equal opportunity policies that mandate fairness in recruitment, promotions, and project assignments are vital to creating a balanced and diverse workforce. Respondent 6 emphasises that "*for true diversity, women must be included deliberately and strategically, not just as a token gesture but as an integral part of the organisation.*"

4. Flexible Work Arrangements: Providing flexible work options like remote work and supportive policies like maternity/paternity leave can help women balance professional and personal responsibilities. Respondent 11 highlights the importance of "*introducing flexible work options and supportive policies (e.g., maternity/paternity leave, virtual work) to accommodate diverse needs.*"

10. ENCOURAGING GENDER INCLUSIVITY IN CORPORATE CULTURE

1. Mentorship Programs: Structured mentorship programs for women can help them advance their careers by providing guidance, support, and insights. Respondent 12 states, "*Mentorship programs tailored for*

women can provide the guidance and support needed to advance in their careers."

2. Flexible Work Arrangements: Flexible work arrangements, such as remote work and flexible hours, are essential for accommodating work-life balance, particularly benefiting women with additional familial responsibilities. Respondent 11 agrees that "introducing flexible work options and supportive policies... can help women balance their professional and personal lives better."

3. Transparent Performance Metrics: Developing and implementing transparent performance metrics is essential for objectively assessing employee contributions and reducing biases in evaluations and promotions. Respondent 5 mentions, "There should be metrics to ensure they are actively working towards greater gender inclusivity."

11. CONCLUSION

A strong emphasis on gender diversity and inclusivity marks Nigeria's corporate governance evolution. As Nigeria continues its corporate governance journey, stakeholders must remain proactive in adapting governance systems to meet the challenges of a dynamic business environment. Integrating gender-inclusive policies, regulatory frameworks, and corporate best practices is essential for promoting inclusive governance standards, gender diversity, and sustainable business practices. By leveraging these opportunities and addressing ongoing challenges, Nigerian companies can foster a more inclusive and equitable corporate landscape that enhances organisational effectiveness and long-term growth.

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